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Muxandis ijtimoiy kompetensiyasi va uni rivojlantirish yo'nalishlari

Nuriddinov Mirsaid Abdumannonovich

Farg'ona davlat texnika universiteti katta o'qituvchisi

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada mehnat bozorida talaba-yoshlar faolligini kuchaytirish, talabalar kompetentligi masalalari, ularning ijtimoiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishning dolzarb masalalari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: mehnat bozori, ijtimoiy kompetensiya, muxandis, talabalar kompetentligi

Социальная компетентность инженера и направления ее развития

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Аннотация. В данной статье описаны важные вопросы усиления активности студентов и молодежи на рынке труда, вопросы компетентности студентов, развития их социальной компетентности.

Ключевые слова: рынок труда, социальная компетентность, инженер, компетентность студента

Social competence of an engineer and directions of its development

Nuriddinov Mirsaid Abdumannonovich

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Annotation. In this article, the important issues of strengthening the activity of students and youth in the energy labor market, the issues of social competence of students, and the development of their social competence are described.

Key words: labor market, social competence, engineer, student competence

Bugungi kunda energetika mehnat bozorida kuchli raqobatga bardoshli bo'lgan kadrlarga bo'lgan extiyoj kundan kunga ortib bormoqda. Bu esa nafaqat professor-o'qituvchilar mas'uliyatini oshirish, balki yetuk energetika soxasida yetuk mutaxassis bo'lishni oldiga maqsad qilgan har bir talabadan kasbiy kompetentlikka ega bo'lish va bozor talablariga muvofiq takomillashib borishni talab etmoqda.

Energetika soxasi mutaxassislari ijtimoiy kompetentligining qay darajada ekanligi talabalik davrida ijtimoiy moslashuvchanlik, o'zaro muloqot, faoliyatni yo'lga qo'yish jarayonida anglanadi va bo'lajak energetik uchun muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Bo'lajak energetikning ijtimoiy kompetensiyasi- bu texnik oliy o'quv yurti energetika soxasi talabasining kasbiy tayyorgarligi natijasida yuzaga keladigan shaxsiy xususiyat bo'lib, bunda uning ijtimoiy hayot va faoliyatga tayyorligi, bilimlari, ko'nikmalari, ijtimoiy me'yorlar va qadriyatli yondoshuvlarni o'zlashtirish ko'nikmalari, kasbiy va ijtimoiy muhitni bashorat qilish xamda samarali o'zaro munosabatda bo'lish, ishlab chiqarish jarayonini qulay va samarali tashkil etish, kasbiy muammolarni hal qilishni ta'minlash, shaxsiy va ijtimoiy farovonlik uchun mas'uliyatli bo'lish imkonini beradi.

Bugungi kunda energetika soxasidagi tub o'zgarishlar, qayta tiklanuvchi va ekologik xavfsiz energiya manbaalariga bo'lgan extiyoj, davlatimiz tomonidan soxaga berilayotgan e'tibor va imkoniyatlar ko'plab yoshlarimizni ushbu kasb egasi bo'lishga undamoqda. Lekin, oliy ta'lim tizimiga kirib kelgach energetika soxasiga oid fundamental va kasbiy bilimlarni egallash bilan cheklanib qolish, ya'ni ijtimoiy kompetensiyaning yetarli shakllanmasligi soxa bitiruvchilarini kelajakda o'z imkoniyatlarini yetarli anglamaslik va ulardan unumli foydalanish imkoniyatining cheklanishiga sabab bo'lmoqda. Xo'sh, talabalar ijtimoiy kompetensiyasini qanday rivojlantirish mumkin?

Talabalar ijtimoiy kompetentligiga o'z oldiga maqsad qo'yish, unga erishishda yuqori darajada kuch-g'ayrat, shijoat, jo'shqinlikni namoyon etish orqali erishiladiki, bu jarayon bir qator omillar bilan bog'liqdir.

Talabalar ijtimoiy kompetentligini rivojlantirishda quyidagi omillarga asoslanish zarur:

- o'z-o'zini anglashning yuksak darajasi;
- fuqarolik, o'z qadr-qimmatini his qilish, o'zini hurmat qilish, intizomlilik, to'g'rilik;
- qarorlar qabul qilishda mustaqillik va ma'suliyatni his qilish;
- hayotiy faoliyat mazmunini erkin tanlash;
- mehribonlik, yaxshilik; alturizm, sabrlilik, chidamlilik, kamtarlik;
- bilish va o'z-o'zini anglash, go'zallik, refleksiya, muloqot va hayot mazmunini chuqur tushunishga ehtiyoj;

- faoliyat o'zgartiruvchi ilmiy bilimlar, malakalar, ko'nikmalar, intellekt, institutsiya, ijodiy hayotga ehtiyoj;
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- chet tillarni o'rganish;
- milliy va diniy urf-odatlarini bilish;
- sog'lom turmush tarzi;
- jismoniy toblanish;
- estetik did, yaxshi amallar;
- tadbirkorlik, raqobatbardoshlik, boshqarish qobiliyati;
- kirishimlilik;
- ijodiy professional fikrlash qobiliyati, tarixni, turli xalqlar madaniyatini bilish va hokazo.

Yuqoridagi omillarning bo'lajak energetiklar tomonidan o'z vaqtida va mukammal o'zlashtirilishi, shuningdek, o'z mehnat faoliyatlari jarayonida muntazam qo'llanilib borilishi nafaqat ularning jamoadagi o'rni va mavqeining oshib borishiga, balki o'zini jamoaning ajralmas qismi ekanligini doim xis qilib borishi, jamiyatdan mamnunlik va qoniqish xissining mustaxkamlanib borishiga va oxir oqibatda jamiyatning yetik mutaxassisi sifatida tom ma'noda o'z yurtining vatanparvariga aylanishiga olib kelishi shubxasiz.

Demak, ijtimoiy kompetensiyani rivojlantirish mahorat va ishbilarmonlik bilan jamiyat ehtiyojlarini qondira oladigan bo'lajak mutaxassisni, pirovard natijada esa vatanparvar, komil insonni voyaga yetkazishdir.

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